

Letter to the Editor

Trimetallic coordination compounds of alkali metals with anhydrous nickel(II) and copper(II) salicylate

Our attention was drawn to a publication in our journal by Sheo Satya Prakash, Deepa Bariar, J. Kumar, Manilal, Syed Khalid Mustafa and Nilima Dhar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2008, **85**, 205-207 in which the authors have reported the synthesis and characterization of trimetallic coordination compounds of the type $[\text{Ma}(\text{HL})_2 \cdot 2\text{MbL}]$ where Ma = copper(II) or nickel(II), HL = salicylic acid, Mb = Li^+ , Na^+ and K^+ , and L = α -nitroso- β -naphthol, 8-hydroxyquinoline, NaSCN and KBr.

The reported magnetic moments by Prakash *et al.*¹ for their coordination compounds are erroneous since the magnetic susceptibilities have not been corrected for temperature independent paramagnetism term (TIP). Prakash *et al.*¹ have reported the room temperature magnetic moments in the range 2.00–2.20 B.M. for their copper(II) coordination compounds of the type $[\text{Cu}(\text{HL})_2 \cdot 2\text{M}'\text{L}]$ (where $\text{M}' = \text{Li}^+$, Na^+ and K^+ , HL = salicylic acid, L = α -nitroso- β -naphthol, 8-hydroxyquinoline, NaSCN and KBr) and have used these magnetic moment values to indicate that there is no metal-metal interaction in these compounds. I would like to point out that from the room temperature magnetic moment for copper(II) coordination compounds, one can not predict the absence of metal-metal interaction. Even a weak antiferromagnetic type of magnetic exchange interaction through the out of plane magnetic exchange interaction via the $d_{z^2}(\text{Cu})$ – $d_{z^2}(\text{Cu})$ overlap may lower the magnetic moment of a copper(II) coordination compound from 2.2 B.M. to a lower value in the expected range (1.78–2.20 B.M.)² of room temperature magnetic moment for the copper(II) coordination compounds. A ferromagnetic type of magnetic exchange interaction may increase the magnetic moment of a copper(II) coordination compound from 1.78 B.M. to a higher value in the above expected range of room temperature magnetic moment.

Although Prakash *et al.*¹ have presented trimetallic structures for their copper(II) and nickel(II) coordination compounds, they have failed to give any proof of trimetallic structures from molecular weight, mass spectra, infrared spectra and X-ray studies. The reported synthetic methods for their trimetallic copper(II) and nickel(II) coordination compounds are not suitable for reproduction elsewhere since the amount

of starting materials and solvents used and yield are missing.

Prakash *et al.*¹ have assigned an infrared spectral band at around 1335 cm^{-1} to the phenolic OH bending mode in the ligand and copper(II) and nickel(II) coordination compounds. This assignment is erroneous for the reason that one does not expect a bending mode in a diatomic system like OH. Their assignment of an infrared spectral band at 1568 – 1595 cm^{-1} to $\nu_{\text{asy}}(\text{COO})$ is erroneous since $\nu(\text{C}=\text{C})$ interferes. Therefore, these coordination compounds have not been characterized properly by infrared spectra. Nor they have found out the bonding pattern of NaSCN and KBr with Mb (where Mb = Li^+ , Na^+ and K^+).

Prakash *et al.*¹ have indicated that the “magnetic, spectral and infrared spectral data suggest that they are oxygen bridged trinuclear complexes”, they have not given any magnetic, electronic spectral and infrared spectral data which support the presence of an oxygen bridged trinuclear structure. In fact the structure presented for their copper(II) and nickel(II) coordination compounds indicates that there does not exist any oxygen bridge $[\text{M} \cdots \text{O} \cdots \text{M}']$ (usually called oxo bridge) or $\text{M} \cdots \text{O} \cdots \text{O} \cdots \text{M}'$ (usually called peroxo bridge) in these coordination compounds but the structure of these coordination compounds proposed by Prakash *et al.*¹ contains hydroxyl bridge ($\text{M} \cdots \text{OH} \cdots \text{M}'$) and carboxylate bridge ($\text{M} \cdots \text{OOCO} \cdots \text{M}'$).

Prakash *et al.*¹ have reported three *d-d* bands at 10000, 14815 and 28571 cm^{-1} in anhydrous nickel(II) salicylate and have used these bands to predict octahedral structure for nickel(II) salicylate without citing any reference in support of their this prediction and without even assigning these bands to specific transitions. We assign these bands to the transitions ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$ (ν_1), ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ (ν_2) and ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ (ν_3), respectively in an octahedral environment³. We fail to understand how this four-coordinated coordination compound ($[\text{Ni}(\text{HSal})_2]$) can exhibit the electronic spectral bands characteristics of octahedral nickel(II) coordination compounds. We also fail to understand how this supposedly octahedral coordination compound is changed into a tetrahedral coordination compound in $[\text{Ni}(\text{HL})_2 \cdot 2\text{MbL}]$ with no apparent bond breaking. The journey of the four-coordinate nickel(II) salicylate to octahedral nickel(II) salicylate (as

indicated from erroneous electronic spectral data discussed later) to tetrahedral nickel(II) in $[\text{Ni}(\text{HL})_2 \cdot 2\text{Mbl}]$ (as indicated from magnetic and spectral data) seems to be a magical chemistry and this chemistry and its mechanism have not been explained by Prakash *et al.*¹ scientifically. The $\nu_2:\nu_1$ ratio for $[\text{Ni}(\text{HSal})_2]$ calculated by us from the spectral band positions reported by Prakash *et al.*¹ is 1.48. After considering the electronic spectral data of a large number of octahedral nickel(II) coordination compounds of weak field as well as strong field ligands, it has been established beyond doubt that the $\nu_2:\nu_1$ ratio in the octahedral nickel(II) coordination compounds lies *invariably* in the range (1.60–1.82)^{4,5}. The significantly low value (1.48) of the $\nu_2:\nu_1$ ratio for the octahedral nickel(II) coordination compound of salicylic acid indicates that the spectral band positions (ν_1 and ν_2) reported by Prakash *et al.*¹ for nickel(II) salicylate are erroneous. In order to test the validity of the electronic spectral band positions reported by Prakash *et al.*¹, we have calculated the electronic spectral parameters for nickel(II) salicylate using the established procedure^{5,6}. The electronic spectral parameters for nickel(II) salicylate as calculated by us are as follows^{5,6}: $Dq = 1000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $B' = 55.10 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $B = B'/B = 0.052$ (where $B = 1056 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ for Ni^{2+} ion) and $B^0 = (1 - B) \times 100 = 94.80\%$. The data indicate that the Racah parameter (B') for nickel(II) salicylate has undergone a reduction of 94.80% in comparison to the free ion value (B) of 1056 cm^{-1} . The reduction of B' in octahedral nickel(II) coordination compounds with the weak field ligands occurring towards the left hand side of the spectrochemical series is unusually less than about 14% (e.g. in $[\text{Ni}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]\text{SO}_4$, it is 14.1%)⁷ while the reduction of B' in the octahedral nickel(II) coordination compounds with strong field ligands occurring towards the right hand side of the spectrochemical series is usually greater than about 29% (e.g. in $[\text{Ni}(\text{dipyridyl})_3]\text{SO}_4$, it is 29.5%)⁷. Since the position of salicylic acid in the spectrochemical series lies between H_2O and dipyrindyl, the reduction of B' in the octahedral nickel(II) coordination compound with salicylic acid is expected to be less than 29.5% in comparison to the free ion value. The unusually extremely high (94.80%) reduction of B' in this nickel(II) coordination compound is absurd and indicates that the spectral band positions of ν_1 and ν_3 bands reported by Prakash *et al.*¹ are erroneous and cooked up. We have not yet come across an octahedral nickel(II) coordination compound having covalent metal-ligand bonding to

exhibit a reduction of B' so high as 94.80% except for nickel(II) salicylate reported by Prakash *et al.*¹. The nephelauxetic parameter B^0 value for strong field ligands usually lies around 30% (e.g. B^0 value for $[\text{Ni}(\text{dipyridyl})_3]$ is 28%)⁷ while it is around 10% or less for weak field ligands (e.g. B^0 value for $[\text{Ni}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]\text{SO}_4$ is 12%)⁷. Salicylic acid being a weaker ligand than strong field ligands such as dipyrindyl, the B^0 value of nickel(II) salicylate is expected to be less than 30%. The extremely high B^0 value (94.80%) as calculated by us from the spectral band positions reported by Prakash *et al.*¹ indicates that the spectral band positions of ν_1 and ν_3 bands reported by Prakash *et al.*¹ are erroneous and cooked up. The erroneous value of the position of the ν_1 band leads to a lower value (1.48) of the $\nu_2:\nu_1$ ratio than the expected value of the $\nu_2:\nu_1$ ratio of 1.60–1.82 (Ref. 4, 5).

The structure of the coordination compounds $[\text{Ma}(\text{HL})_2 \cdot 2\text{Mbl}]$ (where Ma = copper(II) and nickel(II), Mb = Li^+ , Na^+ , K^+ , HL = salicylic acid, and L = α -nitroso- β -naphthol, 8-hydroxyquinoline, NaSCN and KBr) reported by Prakash *et al.*¹ is erroneous since it contains two carbon atoms whose valency is 3 and the primary valency and the secondary valency of the metal ions have been erroneously indicated.

References

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Arun Syamal

School of Coordination Chemistry
D Wing, Ushanagar, Bhandup
Mumbai-400 078, India
E-mail: arunsyamal@yahoo.co.in
Fax: 91-22-25662430